

fish whose initial population was 37,500 increased in number by 209%; in size, each fish increased by 4 cm. Fish weight

increased considerably during the cropping duration. A higher population reduced the ultimate size of each

individual fish and the total fish yield per hectare. But fish culture had no appreciable effect on the rice yield. ■

Md. Nazrul Islam Miah, M. Zahidul Hoque, and Peter R. Hobbs, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Suitable cultivars for intensive rice-based cropping systems in Bangladesh

Promising cultivars for intensive rice-based multiple cropping systems. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Crops	Best performing cultivars	Potentially acceptable cultivars
Field corn	Thai Comp., No. 1 DMR BC ₃ (S) C1, Early DMR Comp. 2	Thai Comp., No. 1 (S) C ₂ , Early DMR Comp. 1
Sweet corn	Thai Comp. supersweet DMR #1	College sweet synthetic
Sorghum	IS2940, Cosor 2	CS108, Cosor 3, CS100
Pearl millet	ICRISAT-7141NEP-13-5007-2 (OP)	ICRISAT-7142NEP-13-5613-1 (OP)
Peanut	Kidang, SK-38	CES101, P23, EG. Bunchy
Soybean	Davis, Williams (dry season) Bossier, Hardee, Seemes (wet season)	Clark 63, TK5 Williams, Davis
Chickpea	ICRISAT No. 4951, 2784	2836, 4961, 4465
Cowpea	All season	TVU354, TVU201, RDC-6-12W

The Rice Cropping Systems Division initiated research to evaluate and modify the essentially rice-based cropping systems of the BRRI project area. The cultivation of nonrice crops should be incorporated into the existing rice cropping systems to improve the potential cropping patterns for rainfed and irrigated areas. Unfortunately, suitable cultivars for many nonrice crops were not available from local sources. BRRI has no mandate to develop varieties other than those of rice, so the division undertook a

varietal screening program with active participation of relevant national and international organizations.

From 1974 to 1978, varieties of corn, sorghum, pearl millet, peanut, soybean, cowpea, and chickpea were evaluated at

the BRRI experimental farms and in selected farmers' fields of the BRRI project area. Several promising varieties were identified (see table) and are now used in various single and double cropping systems in the area. ■

Evaluation of mung bean cultivars under monoculture and intercropping systems

Md. Nazrul Islam Miah, research fellow; and Virgilio R. Carañgal, network coordinator, Cropping Systems Program, Multiple Cropping Department, International Rice Research Institute

The pulse crop mung bean *Vigna radiata* is grown mostly as monoculture but is

also intercropped with corn and sugarcane or grown under plantation crops such as coconut or rubber. Mung bean is also relayed in wetland rice in most of Southeast Asia. Evaluation of mung bean varieties for varied conditions is imperative because of yield fluctuations due to seasonal and environmental situations. An important question is whether breeders should evaluate varieties

in monoculture or in intercropping systems for maximum testing efficiency.

Ten mung bean varieties were evaluated in monoculture and intercropped with corn in dry- and wet-season trials in 1978-79 at the new upland area of the IRRI experimental farm. Recommended cultural management practices, such as fertilization, weeding, irrigation, and

Yield comparison (kg/ha) of mung bean varieties and their relative ranking for monoculture and when intercropped with corn. IRRI, 1978-79 dry season and 1979 wet season.^a

Mung bean variety	1978-79 dry season				1979 wet season			
	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank
EG-MG-174-3	850 a	1	203	2	873 abc	5	465 abc	6
CES 55	638 ab	2	213	1	779 bc	8	377 c	8
S8 (Green)	619 b	3	160	5	671 c	10	363 c	9
M350	601 b	4	135	7	1055 a	2	525 abc	4
CES-1T-2	589 b	5	178	3	1061 a	1	667 a	1
CES-14	561 b	6	137	6	821 abc	7	387 bc	7
CES-U-1	534 b	7	168	4	694 c	9	315 c	10
MG-50-10A (Y)	490 b	8	115	10	1024 ab	3	478 abc	5
CES-1D-21	475 b	9	127	9	877 abc	4	611 a	2
CES-1F-5	449 b	10	129	8	871 abc	6	598 ab	3
Mean	580		157 ns		873		478	
CV (%)	23		42		18		21	

^ans = not significant. In a column means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

spraying of fungicide and insecticide were used.

The varieties that yielded high in monoculture also yielded high when intercropped with corn in both seasons (see table). When the varieties were ranked on the basis of yield performance in the tests, among the five top yielders in monoculture in the dry season were EG-MG-174-3, CES 55, S8 (Green), M350, and CES-1T-2. When intercropped with corn, the top yielders were CES 55, EG-MG-174-3, CES-1T-2, CES-U-1, and

S8 (Green). The test varieties performed differently in the wet season. The five top yielders for monoculture were CES-1T-2, M350, MG-50-10A (Y), CES-1D-21, and EG-MG-174-3. In intercropping, the top yielders were CES-1T-2, CES-1D-21, CES-1F-5, M350, and MG-50-10A (Y).

In the dry season, correlations of mung bean yields and rank orders for monocrops vs corn association gave positive and significant r values ($r=0.75^*$ for yield, and $r=0.80^{**}$ for rank order). Varieties also exhibited similar

relationships in the wet-season planting ($r=0.74^*$ for yield, and $r=0.88^{**}$ for rank order). Correlations of mung bean yields and rank orders for monocrops vs intercrops over two seasons were also found significant at the 1% level of significance ($r=0.88^{**}$ for yield, and $r=0.82^{**}$ for rank order). Although seasons influence the yield and cultivar ranking, promising mung bean varieties can be screened in monoculture and recommendations for other associated systems can be made. ■

Reducing turnaround time and cost of production by zero and minimum tillage in intensive rice cropping systems

M. Zahidul Hoque and Raisuddin Akanda, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

A longer turnaround time has been one of the most important constraints to intensive rice cropping patterns, particularly those involving modern rice varieties, in Bangladesh. Farmers usually keep a turnaround time of 2–3 weeks between rice crops. The later part of the period is often used for land preparation. Four tillage treatments were used in an experiment undertaken in 1979 aus in a farmer's field at the BRRI Cropping Systems Research site at Salna to

determine the effect of zero and minimum tillage and reduced turnaround time on the yield of aus (Chandina) rice following a crop of boro (Pajam) rice. Both crops were irrigated. In the experimental aus crop, the farmer applied fertilizer at 56 kg N/ha, 28 kg P_2O_5 /ha, and 28 kg K_2O /ha. Forty-eight percent of the nitrogen and all P_2O_5 and K_2O were applied basally; the rest of the nitrogen was applied in two topdressings. The treatments were replicated twice and received uniform water management, weeding, pest control, and other operations.

A 1-day turnaround period was needed for the zero tillage treatment; a 4-day period for the minimum tillage treatment. High-intensity tillage was

applied within 3-day turnaround time. The farmer plowed 7 times and laddered 4 times during a 15-day turnaround period. There was no significant difference in grain yield due to tillage practice.

However, land preparation for minimum tillage cost \$14.02/ha; that for high-intensity tillage within 3 days, \$60.93/ha; and that for the farmer's level of tillage, \$71.61/ha. The zero tillage practice in the irrigated rice paddies reduced the turnaround time to 1 day without reducing grain yields, thus enabling the farmers to grow more intensive cropping patterns. Expensive land preparation could be totally avoided in the irrigated areas by adopting the zero-tillage technique. ■

Machinery development and testing

Power and cost requirements for field operations in rice cultivation

M. Zahidul Hoque and Md. Raisuddin Akanda, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

The human and animal power requirements for various field operations were monitored during cultivation of the 1979 aus rice crop at the BRRI cropping systems research site, Salna, Dacca district. Detailed records were maintained on the actual human- and animal-hour requirements by using a

stopwatch for the various operations of 12 farmers who grew aus rice (4 used traditional varieties, 8 grew modern ones). The costs of human and paired-animal-hours were computed at the rate of \$0.08 and \$0.17/hour, respectively.

The table shows that 969 human-hours/ha costing \$80.87/ha, and 167 paired-animal-hours/ha costing \$27.87/ha were used for all field operations. Weeding accounted for the highest human-hours (37%), followed by transplanting (19%), harvesting (18%), and plowing (15%). Animal power was used only in plowing (89%) and laddering (11%).

When modern varieties were used, the total human- and paired-animal-hours per hectare were 822 and 254, at a corresponding total cost of \$68.47 and \$42.40. Plowing required the maximum human-hours (29%), followed by harvesting, weeding, and transplanting. Plowing also used 93% animal power. Interestingly, the total per-hectare power costs for the traditional and modern varieties were almost the same. The study showed that plowing, transplanting, weeding, and harvesting were the major field operations requiring 89% of the total power requirements of both traditional and modern varieties. ■